

110 s, with an interval of 10 s to control bran removal (degree of polish). The degree of polish ranged from 0 to 9.05% and 0 to 7.57% for Basmati and UPR79 rice, respectively. The collected bran at the end of each interval of milling was used to extract the oil using Soxtec HT.

The table shows the effect of time of milling on the degree of polish and oil recovery of bran. Oil recovery ranged from 15.70 to 20.91% for Basmati and 14.57 to 17.90% for UPR79. The maximum oil content was observed at 10 s milling time, for which the degree of polish was 3.33% for Basmati and 2.75% for UPR79. For both varieties of rice bran, the oil recovery starts increasing from 0 to 60 s time of milling samples of bran and then decreases from 70 to 110 s. The oil content of both varieties was maximum at 7.83 and 5.81% degree of polish for Basmati and UPR79, respectively. Weight of a rice grain at the end of each time of milling is shown in the table.

Various mathematical models were tested for their suitability (least error prediction criterion) to describe the oil recovery (O_r) of bran. The following model was found to correlate the experimental observations satisfactorily:

$$O_r = aD_p - bD_p^2$$

The coefficients a and b and statistical parameters of the equation are given in the table. In view of the high r value and low associated error, the above model has been accepted and tested for validity in commercial rice mills. ■

Jaymati, a high-yielding summer rice variety with good grain quality for Assam

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Flooding causes a heavy decrease in winter rice area, with a resulting

decline in production and productivity in the state of Assam. There is therefore scope for bringing chronically flood-affected and waterlogged winter rice areas under summer (boro) rice cultivation. With the increase in irrigation facilities, summer rice area is increasing fast. But a suitable summer variety for flood-affected areas must be of 160-170 d duration so that it can be harvested before the onset of flooding in mid-May.

We therefore developed Jaymati (TTB 103-2), a medium-tall (130 cm) rice variety from the cross Jaya / Mahsuri by the pedigree method of breeding. Jaymati is photoperiod-insensitive and suitable for transplanting in summer and autumn, and has well-exserted panicles and a brownish husk. Grains are awnless and medium in size. The variety has a 1,000-grain weight of 20.2 g. Kernels are white, with a nonglutinous endosperm. The

length and width of the kernels are 6.34 mm and 2.16 mm, respectively. Milling recovery is 66.5%. Jaymati is moderately resistant to bacterial blight, gall midge, and stem borer.

The duration of Jaymati from seed to seed is 170 d for summer and 130 d for autumn and winter rice. The variety's good grain quality gives it an advantage for growing autumn rice. Most autumn varieties grown by Assam farmers have coarse grains. Because farmers need a Mahsuri type of grain for autumn cultivation, some farmers grow Mahsuri in autumn. But because its longer growth duration is not suitable in that season, Jaymati would be a better choice.

Jaymati was tested at several locations throughout the state and it performed well as a summer crop (see table). It was recommended for summer cropping in the Central and Brahmaputra Valley zone of Assam by the state for 1996. ■

Yield performance of Jaymati.

Location	Year	Season	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)		
			Jaymati	Jaya/local	LSD (0.05)
RARS, Titabar	1989	Autumn	3.4	3.0	0.70
	1990	Autumn	4.8	3.5	1.00
	1991	Autumn	3.3	3.9	1.25
	1991	Winter	4.4	4.0	1.70
	1991	Summer	3.2	2.2	0.30
National trial					
AICRIP (JET13316), 1991, winter					
Chiplima	-	-	7.7	7.0	1.26
Sindri	-	-	6.0	5.3	1.35
Masodha	-	-	4.3	4.2	0.50
Kanpur	-	-	3.7	2.9	0.26
Rajpur	-	-	2.8	2.8	0.72
Titabar	-	-	4.4	4.0	1.72

Location	Year	Season	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)			
			Jaymati	Mahsuri	Jagliboro	LSD (0.05)
RARS, Shillongani, Nagaon						
	1991-92	Summer	7.3	6.3	4.0	0.65
	1992-93	Summer	6.9	6.2	4.0	0.52
	1993-94	Summer	6.4	6.2	4.0	0.81
On-farm testing						
	1994-95	Summer				
Tokowbari	-	-	6.2	3.2	-	-
Dablongati	-	-	4.0	3.2	-	-
Bengenati	-	-	3.3	3.2	-	-
Bahuabheti	-	-	6.0	4.8	-	-
Pooled average over season and year						
	Autumn		3.83	3.40		
	Winter		4.76	4.31		
	Summer		5.41	3.58		
	Overall		4.88	3.84		